

As the president of Corniche Capital, David Ebrahimzadeh pursues opportunistic investment opportunities across public and private sectors. His firm focuses on generating both current income and long-term strategic results with its private equity and real estate divisions. David Ebrahimzadeh uses creative structuring and in-depth transaction analysis to minimize risk exposure.

[David Ebrahimzadeh](#) grew up in a family heavily involved in real estate. Beginning when he was young, he frequented construction sites and learned about the business from his relatives. His strong family background in real estate has given him an instinct for spotting a great deal and whether a new investment will be profitable.

With a family background in real estate, David Ebrahimzadeh wanted to start something different. He built a successful real estate investment firm from the ground up, and is now giving back to the community via scholarships.

David Ebrahimzadeh, President of Corniche Capital, started the [David Ebrahimzadeh Scholarship](#) to recognize those students who are seeking a degree in real estate, or have a passion in real estate. Ebrahimzadeh created Corniche Capital with the goal of pursuing opportunities in the real estate and private equity sectors. The purpose of this scholarship has a similar goal, by extending an opportunity to those who are seeking to continue their education.

A recipient of a Bachelor's degree in finance from The George Washington University, David Ebrahimzadeh has served as the president of New York-based Corniche Capital since 2003. In this capacity, David Ebrahimzadeh invests in real estate and a diverse selection of private equity transactions. In terms of real estate, the firm invests principally in the multi-family and industrial in the Northeast and Southeast, with an emphasis on value-add opportunities.

Mr. Ebrahimzadeh's minimum deal threshold is \$20 million, and he seeks investments in multifamily, office, and hotel properties. He signed a contract to acquire a dozen convenience stores in New Mexico in 2016. The impetus behind the venture was the opportunity to achieve "contender" status within a competitive but fragmented industry, according to Mr. Ebrahimzadeh. Through streamlining operations, profitability was significantly increased.

David Ebrahimzadeh teamed up with Marcus & Millichap and TZD Retail Group, which acted as exclusive commercial brokerage. Corniche Capital's ultimate goal was to extend its petroleum operations to hundreds of convenience stores in America.

David Ebrahimzadeh, works with private and public sectors, more specifically with real estate and private equity. He started his career early and gained experience fast in business, land acquisition and entitlement, the development and investment process, and property management.

David Ebrahimzadeh has a true passion for [his family business](#). Without that spark, it's difficult to really give your job 100 percent of your effort. He also believes that he is a fair supervisor and that he knows how to run a functional company with few problems.